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IN VITRO ASSESSMENT OF ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITIES OF METHANOL EXTRACT FROM LEAVES OF *GOSSYPIUM HIRSUTUM*

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ABSTRACT

The leaves of Gossypium hirsutum have historically been used to treat wound and a number of bacterial illnesses. Hence, this study seeks to screen the methanol leaf extract of G. hirsutum for its chemical composition, antioxidant and antimicrobial activities in order to find possible sources of novel phytochemicals. Qualitative and quantitative phytochemical screenings were conducted on the extract using standard method. The different phyto compounds in the extract were identified using Gas Chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS). The antioxidant activity of the extract was evaluated using 2,2-diphenyl-1-Picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), Nitric oxide scavenging (NOS) and 2,2-azino-bis-3-ethylbenzo thiozoline-6-sulphonic acid (ABTS) assays while the antimicrobial activity was estimated using the zone of inhibition method. The qualitative phytochemical screening showed that the extract has phenol, flavonoid, terpenoid, steroid, proanthocyanidin, phytate, tannin and saponin while the quantitative screening showed that the extract contains the above-named phytochemicals in different concentration and phenols been the highest $759.66 \pm 16.03\text{mg}/100\text{g}$ of the extract. The GC-MS analysis showed the presence of fifty-one (51) compounds accounting for 99.50% of the total component of the

*crude extract. The major compounds found in the extract include palmitic acid 20.415, caryophyllene 13.65% and α – linolenic acid 13.49%. The methanol leaf extract showed percentage DPPH, ABTS and NOS radical scavenging activity of 44.10 ± 3.20 , 64.06 ± 0.63 and 55.44 ± 0.99 respectively. The extract was active against some *Bacillus* species, *Bacillus polymyxa* (NCTC10343) 17.75 ± 0.25 , *Bacillus stearothermophilus* (NCIB 8222) 14.75 ± 0.75 and *Bacillus cerus* (NCIB 532) 13.50 ± 0.5 . The leaf extract exhibited promising antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, offering a potential source for the discovery and development of novel therapeutic agents.*

KEYWORDS: Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, *Gossypium Hirsutum*, Methanol Extract

INTRODUCTION

Plants are a treasure trove of bioactive compounds that can be harnessed to develop novel drugs (Kumar *et al.*, 2022). These compounds, which are found in various plant parts, possess antimicrobial properties that are essential for therapeutic treatments (Singh *et al.*, 2020). The pharmacological activities of medicinal plants can be attributed to their secondary metabolites, which are smaller molecules compared to primary metabolites (Pavelkova *et al.*, 2020). Secondary metabolites, including alkaloids, terpenoids, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, and cardiac glycosides, have been shown to exhibit antimicrobial and antifungal activities, making them potential candidates for the development of novel drugs (Lu *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, these compounds are relatively less harmful to humans compared to synthetic drugs (Kumar *et al.*, 2022).

Gossypium hirsutum, a perennial medicinal shrub found in Nigeria, belongs to the family *Malvaceae*, despite its economic importance, it is planted annually and removed after harvesting its seed fiber (Balkrisnan *et al.*, 2023). The plant can grow up to 1.5-2.0 meters in height and is commonly found in southwest Nigeria, where it is planted around homes (Efloras, 2019). *G. hirsutum* has been used in traditional medicine for various purposes, including treating malaria, wounds, and bacterial illnesses. The seed of the plant has been reported to contain the antifungal compound gossypol, which is used in Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani medicinal systems to treat various disorders (Chaturvedi and Nag, 2015). The leaves of the plant are used to treat hypertension and irregular menstruation in Suriname's traditional medicine (Salako and Awodele, 2012).

Previous studies have reported the presence of various bioactive compounds in *G. hirsutum*, these include caryophyllene, palmitic acid, and α -linolenic acid (Ogunmola *et al.*, 2024). The plant's leaf extract has been evaluated for its antimicrobial and antioxidant activities, revealing its potential as a natural remedy for various diseases (Mahapatra *et al.*, 2017, Ogunmola *et al.*, 2023).

This study aimed to identify and quantify the bioactive compounds present in the methanol leaf extract of *G. hirsutum*, which are responsible for its medicinal properties.

METHODOLOGY

• Collection and Processing of Plant Sample

Fresh leaves of *G. hirsutum* were collected from Kolobo area, (7.8544489⁰N, 3.98185⁰E, Oyo town, Oyo state, Nigeria, in October 2022. The sample was identified and authenticated at the Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN), Ibadan, and allocated Voucher number FHI 113772. The leaf sample was washed with distilled water, air-dried for seven days at room temperature, and pulverized using an electric blender. The pulverized sample was stored in a polythene bag at 4°C until analysis.

- **Extraction of the Crude extracts**

The pulverized sample (1000g) was weighed and steeped in methanol for 48 hours, filtered through Whatman No 1 filter paper and concentrated using a rotary evaporator at 25°C. The extracts were stored in firmly tight bottles and kept in a refrigerator until the time of analysis.

- **Qualitative Phytochemical Screening**

The qualitative Phytochemical screening of the leaf extracts were conducted using documented methods for the detection of phytochemical components (Gunjal, 2020). The Presence of saponin, flavonoids, alkaloid, phenol, tannins, phytate, steroids, terpenoids and proanthocyanidins were tested for.

- **Test for saponins**

Foam test: Precisely 5mL of extract are added to 5mL of water and heat, froth forms to indicate the presence of saponin

- **Test for alkaloids**

Hager's test: To 2 mL of extract, precisely 2 drops of Hager's reagent was applied. When there is yellow precipitate, alkaloid is present.

- **Test for Phenols**

Precisely 4 mL of the extract was subjected to 1 mL of concentrated sulphuric acid and a few drops of sodium nitrate (NaNO₃). The mixtures received a precise addition of 2 mL of sodium hydroxide. The presence of phenol was revealed by the production of a blue precipitate. (Iwu *et al.*, 2018)

- **Test for tannins**

Precisely 2 mL of extract was combined with 2 mL of water; and two to three drops of 5% FeCl₃ were added. The green precipitate indicated the presence of tannin.

- **Test for Phytate**

Neogen phytic acid test kit was used. If phytate is present, a blue precipitate forms after precisely 0.5 mL of acetic acid and 2 drops of Neogen kit is applied to 1 ml of the extract.

- **Test for steroids**

2 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ and 2 mL of CHCl₃ were combined with exactly 2 mL of extract. The presence of steroids is shown by reddish-brown ring at the intersection.

- **Test for Terpenoids**

In order to create a layer, precisely 5 mL of the extract was combined with 2 mL of chloroform and 3 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄. When the colour of the layer created turned a deep crimson, terpenoids is present.

➤ **Test for proanthocyanidins**

By staining the extract with a recently made 1% vanillin-6-M HCl solution, proanthocyanidins become evident. If proanthocyanidin is present in the extract, a noticeable red coloration appears. (Engstrom *et al.*, 2014),

- **Test for flavonoids.** One mL of 10% PbC₂H₃O₂ was mixed with exactly 1 mL of the extract. If a yellow hue appears, flavonoids are present.

• **Quantitative Phytochemical Screening**

The methanol leaf extract was subjected to quantitative phytochemical screening using standard Procedures.

➤ **Quantification of total Phenolic Content**

The phenolic content of the extracts was examined using spectrophotometric method (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2020). The analyses were carried out in triplicate and the results were expressed as mg of gallic acid equivalent 100g of dry material.

➤ **Quantification of total flavonoid Content**

The method of Ordonez *et al.*, 2006 was employed to determine the flavonoids content. All the analyses was carried out in triplicate and expressed as mg rutin equivalent.

➤ **Quantification of total tannin Content**

Tannin determination was done according to the method described by Makkar *et al.*, 2020 with minor alterations, using tannic acid as a standard. The tannin content was expressed as tannic acid equivalent in mg per 100g of dry material.

➤ **Quantification of total Phytate**

Quantification of phytate from the sample was carried out following a modified procedure of Harland and Oberleas (1977).

➤ **Quantification of total saponins Content**

The spectro photometric method of Brunner (1984) was used for the saponin determination

➤ **Quantification of Steroid Content**

Steroid content of the leaf extracts was determined using the method described by Trease and Evans (1989)

➤ **Quantification of total terpenoid Content**

The total terpenoid content of the extract was determined using the method described in our earlier publication Ogunmola *et al.*, 2024.

• **Determination of total Proanthocyanidin Content**

Total Proanthocyanidin content was determined using the procedure indicated by Son *et al.*, (1999),

➤ **GC-MS determination of bioactive compounds**

The GC-MS instrument used was Perkin Elmer Turbo mass spectrophotometer (Norwalk, CT06859, and U.S.A) with XLGC. The column used was Perkin Elmer Elite-5 capillary column, measuring 30m x 0.25mm with a film thickness of 0.25mm consisting of dimethyl polysiloxane. Helium at a flow rate of 0.5ml/mn was used as a carrier gas, 250°C of inlet temperature was maintained while the oven temperature was programmed to an initial temperature of 110°C for four (4) min after which it was increased to 240°C, and then programmed to increase to 280°C at a rate of 20°C ending with five (5) minutes. The total time used to run per sample was ninety minutes. Chemical components of these extracts were identified on the basis of their individual retention times with a reference to homologues series of *n*-alkanes in the robust NIST Library 2014. The mass spectra fragmentation of the compounds was compared to the available data (McLafferty, 1989; Adams, 1997; Joulain and Konig, 1998).

IN VITRO ANTIOXIDANT ACTION

- **DPPH Assay**

The antioxidant and radical-scavenging properties of *G. hirsutum* extract was evaluated in relation to the free radical DPPH. The synthetic antioxidants vitamin C, gallic acid, and vitamin E were incubated with a DMSO solution of DPPH for approximately half an hour at room temperature and in the dark. The concentrations of the extracts ranged from 0.0025 to 0.8 mg/mL. Using a vortex machine, the solutions were meticulously mixed, and each sample's absorbance was measured at 517 nm. The following equation was used to determine the extract's capacity to scavenge DPPH-free radicals in the solution.

$$\text{DPPH Scav activity} = \frac{\text{Abs control} - \text{Abs sample}}{\text{Abs control}} \times 100$$

Where Abs control is the absorbance of DPPH + methanol;

Abs sample is the absorbance of DPPH radical + sample extract or standard. The results were expressed in percentages: inhibition = DPPH scavenging activity (%).

The dose-response curve was plotted, and the IC₅₀ value of the synthetic antioxidant and the extracts were calculated (Larayetan *et al.*, 2019).

- **ABTS Assay:**

The extracts' ABTS activity was assessed using the modified Witayapen technique (Nantitanon *et al.*, 2007). After oxidising the ABTS stock solution (7 mM) and adding 2.4 mM of potassium per sulphate in comparable proportions, the combination was allowed to react for 12 h at 25 °C to obtain the working solution. After 7 minutes, using a spectrophotometer, a fraction (1 mL) of the resulting solution was further diluted with 60 mL of methanol to get an absorbance of 0.706 ± 0.001 at 734 nm. In summary, each extract was combined with a methanolic ABTS solution at five distinct concentrations (0.025, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, and 0.4 mg mL⁻¹) and left for seven minutes at 25 °C in the dark. After that, the absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 734 nm, and the

inhibition of the ABTS radical by the extract and commercial antioxidants (Vitamin C and β -carotene) were computed using the DPPH assay equation.

- **Nitric oxide scavenging assay**

The nitric oxide scavenging activity was performed using the method established by Rai *et al.* (2006). A mixture of 0.5 mL of 10 mM sodium nitroprusside in phosphate-buffered saline and varying amounts of the extracts (0.025, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, and 0.4 mg mL⁻¹) was added. The mixture was then incubated for 150 minutes at room temperature in the dark. In this experiment, the sample for the control was precisely 1 mL of water. Following the incubation period, 1 mL of the sulfanilic acid reagent (0.33% sulfanilic acid in 20% glacial acetic acid) was mixed with 0.5 mL of the reaction mixture. After incubating for 5 minutes, add 1 mL of 0.1% naphthyl ethylenediamine dihydrochloride, stir, and incubate for 30 minutes at 25 °C. We measured the absorbance of the resultant chromophore at 540 nm. The nitric oxide scavenging capability of the extract was tested using the Trolox standard curve; the result was expressed as mole Trolox equivalent (TE) antioxidant capacity per 100 g sample. Three copies of each analysis were performed.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Abs control} - \text{Abs sample}}{\text{Abs control}} \times 100$$

- **Agar Well Diffusion Assay**

The agar-well diffusion method was used to examine the antibacterial activities of the crude extracts (Collins *et al.*, 2004). The microorganisms employed in this investigation were injected into nutritional broth (Oxoid), and they were then left to grow for 24 hours at a temperature of 37.0°C. A sufficient amount of Muller Hilton Agar (Oxoid) was placed in sterile petri plates and allowed to solidify in an aseptic environment. Five 6 mm-diameter wells were evenly spaced across freshly made and hardened Mueller Hilton agar (Oxoid) in petri dishes using a sterilized cork borer. The test organisms were [*Staphylococcus aureus* (NCIB 8588), *Clostridium sporogenes* (NCIB 532), *Bacillus cereus* (NCIB 532), *Morganella morganii* (NTCT 235), *Serratia marcescens* (NCIB 1377), *Proendencia rettgeri* (NTCT 1180), *Pseudomona aeruginosa* (NCIB 950), *Micrococcus luteus* (NCIB 196), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (NCIB 418), *Bacillus stearothermophilus* (NCIB 8222), *Proteus vulgaris* (NCIB 67), *Bacillus subtilis* (NCIB 3610), *Salmonella typhimurium* (ATCC 14028), *Proteus mirabilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (NCIB 25923), and *Bacillus polymyxa* (NCTC 10343)]. Exactly 0.1 mL of the extracts were seeded on the outside of the appropriate solid medium in each of the petri dishes using a sterilized swab after the bacterial culture was adjusted to the 0.5 McFarland turbidity standard. The crude extracts generated from the stock were prepared in various quantities ranging from 0.04 to 0.025 mg/ mL, injected into each of the wells, and labeled properly. The petri dishes with the test organism were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The individual wells in each petri dish were checked for zones of growth inhibition, and the average diameter of these zones was determined in millimeters. All tests were performed in triplicates under hygienic conditions. Streptomycin was employed as a positive standard drug.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- Percentage Yield of Crude Extracts**

Exactly 1000g of the powdered leaf sample was used for the extraction and the percentage yield is expressed using the equation

$$\% \text{ yield} = \frac{\text{wt of the crude extract}}{\text{wt of the powered sample}} \times 100$$

The percentage yield is 4.49% and is reported in table 1

Table 1: Percentage yield of the extract

Methanol (g)	%
44.90	4.49

- Phytochemical screening of the Methanol leaf extract of *G. hirsutum***

The qualitative phytochemical screening of the methanol leaf extract of *G. hirsutum* showed the presence of phenol, flavonoid, Terpenoid, steroid, proanthocycindin, phytate, tannin and saponin, however alkaloid was absent in the extract as shown in table 2. This result agrees with the previous works of Omojasola and Awe, 2004, Ademilua and Okpoma, 2018. Bioactive compounds have been reported to have free radical scavenging ability and resistance to microbial pathogens.

Table 2: Qualitative Phytochemical Screening of Leaf Extracts of *G. hirsutum*

Phytochemicals	Saponin	Alkaloid	Phenol & Tannins	Phytate	Steroids & Terpenoids	Proantho-cyaniding	flavonioids
Presence	+	-	+	+	+	+	+

Key: + Present; - Absent

The quantitative phytochemical screening of methanol leaf extract of *G. hirsutum* showed that the extract is rich in phenol, flavonoid, tannin, phytate, saponin, steroid, terpenoid and proanthocyanidin in different concentrations as shown in table 3. The total phenol in the extract is 759.66 ± 16.03 mg/100g, phenols are secondary metabolites synthesised through the shikimic acid and phenyl propanoid pathways. They posse numerous bioactive properties which include antibacterial and antioxidant activities (Okodu *et al.*, 1994). The extract has a total flavonoid concentration of 663.90 ± 9.91 mg/100g. Flavonoid are polyphenol secondary metabolites found

in plant which exhibit significant anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic and anticancer activities (Grozier and Ashiharu, 2006). Also the extract has 66.45 ± 10.29 mg/100g of tannin and this agrees with the works of Omojasola and Awe, (2004) which reported the presence of tannin in significant quantity in *G. hirsutum*, however Ade-Ademilua reported the absence of tannin in this plant. Tannin has antioxidant and anti inflammatory actions in animals (Tong *et al.*, 2022).

Moreover, the concentrations of total phytate, saponin, steroid, terpenoid and proanthocyanidin are 199.56 ± 2.40 , 14.55 ± 0.44 , 151.90 ± 3.17 , 221.30 ± 3.30 and 170.07 ± 9.91 mg/100g respectively. This is the first time phytate will be reported in significant amount in the extract of *G. hirsutum*.

Table 3: Quantitative phytochemical Screening of methanol Leaf Extract of *G. hirsutum*

Phytochemical	Phenol mg/100g	Flavonoid mg/100g	Tannin mg/100g	Phytate mg/100g	Saponin mg/100g	Steroid mg/100g	Terpenoid mg/100g	Proanthocyanidin mg/100g
Concentration	759.66 ± 16.03	663.90 ± 9.91	478.65 ± 12.97	199.56 ± 2.40	14.55 ± 0.44	151.90 ± 3.17	221.30 ± 3.30	170.07 ± 9.91

GC-MS Analysis of methanol leaf extract of *G. hirsutum*.

As indicated in table 4, the GC-MS analysis of methanol leaf extract of *G. hirsutum* revealed the presence of fifty-one compounds which account for 99.51% of the total crude extract. The extract consists of 16 compounds in substantial amount and 35 compounds with percentages less than one. The major compounds include; Hexadecanoic acid (Palmitic acid) (20.41%), caryophyllene (13.65%), α -linolenic acid (13.49%), sitosterol (7.07%) and Ethanamine, 2[[[ethenylylsulfonyl] methoxy] methyl] sulfonyl] –N, N-dimethyl-methoxy] methyl] sulfonyl] –N, N-dimethyl – (5.36%). Some compounds with smaller concentrations include; 2-Butoxyethylacetate (0.22%), Dodecatrien-1-01-, 3,7,11 – trimethyl (0.22%), Ergosta-4, 7, 22-trien-3-one and campesterol (0.21%).

Palmitic acid is a 16 carbon saturated fatty acid most abundant in the body of humans, it is synthesised endogenously from other fatty acids, carbohydrates or acquired through the diet) inappropriate consumption of this fatty acid can trigger the development of cancer as well as the progression of the disease while adequate consumption can reduce the risk of disease (Ortega and Campos, 2021). The value reported in this study aligns with what was reported for *G. barbadense* seed oil (21%) (Krishnaveni *et al.*, 2014) and *Gossypium herbaceum* ethanol leaf extract 18.96% (Larayetan *et al.*, 2021).

Caryophyllene is a bicyclic sesquiterpene found naturally in plants and it contributes to the aroma of the plants (Jitovetz *et al.*, 2002). It is the most abundantly produced terpene in nature and it acts as a cannabinoid. It has been documented to have anti inflammatory action, it efficiently fight against cancer (Blowman *et al.*, 2018) and it has been given GRAS (generally regarded as safe) designation by the Food and Drug Agency and has been approved for use as a food additive, typically for flavouring (<https://ntp...> 14, CFR-code of Federal Regulating (Schmitt, 2016). The value reported in this work is at variance with what was reported for *Gossypium herbaceum* ethanol leaf extract 4.24% (Larayetan *et al.*, 2021).

α – linolenic acid is an C18 n-3 essential polyunsaturated fatty acid that have anti-inflammatory and pro-resolution effect (Srivastava, *et al.*, 2021), it also has anti-diabetic, antioxidant, hepato protective and anti-cancer activities (Srivastava *et al.*, 2021).

β -sitosterol is a white waxy powder predominantly made by plants and is structurally similar to cholesterol. Clinical and prechemical studies suggest that β -sitosterol lower the level of bad cholesterol (LDL) and reduces the risk of coronary artery disease, atherosclerosis, heart attack and it prevents many types of cancer (Le Goff *et al.*, 2019).

Table 4: Chemical composition of methanol leaf extract of *G. hirsutum*

S/N	R.T	Compound	% composition
1.	1.253	1-methoxy-3, 4-dinitrobenzene	0.24
2.	1.327	Azetidine, 1-chloro	0.87
3.	1.419	N1, N1-Dimethyl-N2-(1-phenyl-ethyl)-ethanediamine	2.17
4.	1.562	5-Methoxybenzofurazan, 1-oxide	0.32
5.	2.191	1-(4-Amino-furazan-3-yl) 5-dimethyl amino methyl-1H-(1,2,3) triazole-4-carboxylic acid	0.41
6.	2.432	Caprylic acid	3.68
7.	2.558	Ethanamine, 2[[[(ethenyl sulfonyl) methoxy] methyl] sulfonyl] – N, N-dimethyl-	5.36
8.	3.971	Butyloxitol	3.63
9.	4.926	2-Butoxyethyl acetate	0.22
10.	5.344	Cyclohexane, 1-methyl-4-(1-methylethlidene	0.30

11.	6.099	Copaene	1.16
12.	6.277	Caryophyllene	13.65
13.	6.403	Humulene	2.06
14.	6.511	Cyclohexane, 1-methyl-4-(1-methylethlidene	0.44
15.	6.574	δ -Cadinene	0.59
16.	6.740	4-Heptafluorobutyryloxyhexadecane	0.50
17.	6.998	1-Hexen-3-yne, 2-tert-butyl-	0.50
18.	7.049	2,3-Hexadiene, 2-methyl	0.48
19.	7.158	Dodecatriene-1-ol, 3,7,11-trimethyl	0.22
20.	7.330	Cetene	0.29
21.	7.450	Neophytadiene	2.90
22.	7.518	2-cyclohexen-1-one, 4,4-dimethyl	0.75
23.	7.570	9-Octadecyne	1.63
24.	7.696	Methyl palmitate	0.95
25.	7.827	Palmitic acid	20.41
26.	7.862	3-Eicosene	0.45
27.	8.154	linolenyl alcohol	0.69
28.	8.171	Phytol	0.50
29.	8.280	α -linolenic acid	13.49
30.	8.308	Stearic acid	1.15
31.	8.709	Ethyl-9-cis, 11.trans-octadecadienoate	0.31
32.	8.766	Linolenic acid methylester	0.26
33.	8.823	Decane	0.23
34.	8.955	Octadecane, 3-methyl	0.25
35.	9.081	2-Piperidinone, N-[4-bromo-n-butyl]-	0.22
36.	9.184	3-(3,7-Dimethylocta-2,7-dienyl)-1H indole	0.48
37.	9.224	Bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	2.63
38.	9.853	Terephthalic acid, 4-octylester	0.35
39.	10.088	Supraene	0.96
40.	10.185	Geranyl acetone	0.28
41.	10.259	Alpha-Tocospiro A	0.38
42.	10.345	Alpha-Tocospiro B	0.39
43.	11.306	Beta-Tocopherol	0.54
44.	11.564	Ergosta-4,7,22-trien-3-one	0.21
45.	11.690	Stigmasta-3,5-diene	0.47
46.	11.804	dl-alpha-Tocopherol (Vitamin E)	2.29
47.	12.714	Campesterol	0.21
48.	12.914	Cholesta-22,24-dien-5-ol, 4,4-dimethyl	1.14
49.	13.504	Sitosterol	7.07
50.	14.001	(E)-2-((8R,8as)-8,8aDimethyl-3,4,6,7,8,8a-hexahydronaphthalen-2 (1H)-ylidene) propanal	0.41
51.	14.494	(-)-beta Elemene	0.92
		Total	99.51

• **Antioxidant activity of Methanol leaf extract of *G. hirsutum***

The methanol leaf extract is effective in scavenging the radicals as shown in table 5 and when compared with Vitamin C and Gallic acid standard ($63.49 \pm 2.62\%$, Vit C, 69.85%, Gallic acid 68.00%). The extract is more effective than Vitamin E standard and the result obtained agreed with the works of Muhammad *et al.*, 2014 which reported similar values in the DPPH and ABTS assays

for some species in the *malvaceae* family (Muhammad *et al.*, 2014, Larayetan *et al.*, 2021). Larayetan *et al.*, 2021 reported IC₅₀ value in the DPPH and NOS assay for *G. herbaceum* ethanol leaf extract at 3.33 and 3.87 µg/mL. The high antioxidant activity reported in this work is due to higher quantities of phytochemicals found in the methanol extract. Antioxidant properties of any plant have been reported to be positively correlated with the amount of flavonoids and Phenolics in a plant extract. (Manach *et al.*, 2005, Zhang *et al.*, 2014, Rahman *et al.*, 2015).

Table 5: Antioxidant activities of the leaf Extract of *G. hirsutum*

Extract	DPPH (%)	Trolox equivalent ABTS (%)	Nitric oxide Scavenging (%)	DPPH mg/ml	ABTS mg/ml	NOS mg/ml
Methanol extract	44.10±3.20	64.06 ± 0.63	55.44 ±0.99	5.24	3.86	4.59
Vit. C	69.85	-	90.26	0.007	-	0.005
Gallic acid	68.00	-	82.01	-	-	0.006
Vit. E	16.92	-	7.40	-	-	0.0067

• **Antimicrobial activity of methanol leaf extract of *G. hirsutum***

The methanol leaf extract of *G. hirsutum* showed varying degree of antimicrobial activities against reference strain gram -positive and gram-negative bacteria as shown in table 6. The extract was active against some *Bacillus* species, *Bacillus polymyxa* (NCTC 10343) 17.75 ± 0.25 mm, *Clostridium sporogenes* (NCIB 532) 15.5 ± 1.50 mm, *Bacillus stearothermophilus* (NCIB 532) 13.50 ± 0.50 mm, however the extract was not active against *Staphylococcus aureus* (NCIB 8588). 0.00 mm, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (NCIB 950) 0.00 mm, *Micrococcus luteus* (NCIB 418). 0.00 mm, *Klebsiella pneumonia* (NCIB 418) 0.00, *Proteus vulgaris* (NCIB 67) 0.00, *Bacillus subtilis* (NCIB 3610), 0.00 mm and *Salmonella typhimurium* (ATCC 14028) 0.00 mm at 30 mg/mL. The antimicrobial activity of the extract (17.75 ± 0.25 mm) was higher than that of the standard drug (14.50 ± 0.50 mm) in *Bacillus polymyxa* (NCTC 10343).

Table 6: Antimicrobial Potentials (Zone of inhibition) of methanol leaf extract of *Gossypium hirsutum*

S/N	Bacteria	Met	Streptomycin
1.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (NCIB 8588)	0.00	16.00 ± 0.00
2.	<i>Clostridium sporogenes</i> (NCIB 532)	15.5 ± 1.50	12.50 ± 0.50
3.	<i>Bacillus cereus</i> (NCIB 532)	13.50 ± 0.5	13.00 ± 1.00
4.	<i>Morganella morganii</i> (NTCT 235)	12.00 ± 0.0	13.50 ± 0.50
5.	<i>Serratia marcescens</i> (NICB 1377)	0.00	0.00
6.	<i>Providencia rettgeri</i> (NTCT 1180)	12.00 ± 0.0	13.50 ± 0.50
7.	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (NCIB 950)	0.00	0.00
8.	<i>Micrococcus luteus</i> (NCIB 196)	0.00	13.50 ± 0.50
9.	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> (NCIB 418)	0.00	0.00
10.	<i>Bacillus stearothermophilus</i> (NCIB 8222)	14.75 ± 0.75	16.00 ± 0.00

11.	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i> (NCIB 67)	0.00	0.00
12.	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (NCIB 3610)	0.00	0.00
13.	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> ATCC14028	0.00	13.50 ± 0.50
14.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (NCIB 25923)	11.50 ± 0.50	12.50 ± 0.50
15.	<i>Bacillus polymyxa</i> (NCTC 10343)	17.75 ± 0.25	14.50 ± 0.50

CONCLUSION

The methanol leaf extract of *G. hirsutum* in this study have demonstrated its medicinal capabilities, the active secondary metabolites found in the extract are responsible for the medicinal potential. The research also identified the leaves of *G. hirsutum* as a rich source of antimicrobial agent and a dietary source of antioxidant.

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